

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D7.3

Sustainability Plan for extended BMS RI ELSI Services

WP7 – Common services to provide support with Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues

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Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the sustainability plan that allows the continuation of the ELSI Services for all BMS beyond the formal termination of the project. This concerns in particular the ELSI Knowledge Base and Helpdesk. Rather than seeking sustainability via new initiatives, the continuation of services is based on the integration of the needs of the BMS community into the established BBMRI ELSI Services by focusing the existing BBMRI services, ensuring a federated structure to collaborate with national (e.g., MRC/UK) or other RI services (e.g., EATRIS pharmaceutical regulatory support) and promoting them accordingly. In following this strategy, CORBEL aims to avoid a duplication of efforts and remains just to the long-term goal to establish a single-entry portal for the benefit of the users.

Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached/this deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) Sustainability Plan

Detailed report on the deliverable

Introduction

This deliverable describes the restructuring of the BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Services to accommodate the needs of the LS RIs and therewith guaranteeing sustainable ELSI services during and beyond the project's life span. Ultimately, the core services (Helpdesk, Knowledge Base, network of experts, collaboration with other units) are ensured by BBMRI-ERIC. New content will be generated through project collaborations and synergies with other organisations from academia and industry.

Background

BBMRI-ERIC's ELSI services started as Common Service ELSI and (following an internal SWOT analysis in 2017 including the considerations of LS RIs and an external review in 2018) were subsequently transformed into an ELSI Services & Research unit in 2019 (see Annex 1).

Identifying and Assessing Tools for ELSI Guidance

Building on the findings of several projects (e.g., ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC, BioMedBridges) in relation to user experiences and needs of ELSI tools, we launched an exploratory user survey in the context of CORBEL: Where do you get support with ELSI questions around data and biosamples? Circulated through the CORBEL BMS RIs, the survey consisted of 24 questions. These aimed to assess if the tools and platforms researchers use in relation to ethical, legal, and societal issues were deemed informative, especially for their daily work. It also aimed to identify which questions are currently left unanswered. Considering the wide distribution of the survey via the CORBEL and all BMS RI mailing lists, the turnout was relatively low with only 36 replies. Nonetheless, the responses were conclusive on some aspects as it allowed to deduce some critical do's and don'ts:

Do's and Don'ts for ELSI Services

- Any tool must be easily accessible (not more than 3 clicks to reach information)
- Its content must be comprehensible to researchers (use non-legalistic language).
- The advice given must be reliable (checked with experts).
- Information must be maintained and updated (do not limit it to the lifespan of one research project).

The assessments clearly showed that the establishment of a single, more user-friendly and sustainable service tailored for a precise user group providing practical guidance for daily research practice was favoured (Mayrhofer & Schlünder 2018).

Context Specific Expertise

As ELSI requests require not only a broad theoretical understanding but also an understanding of the context and national/regional legal framework, no single expert can respond to all user questions. Abstract questions allow only abstract answers that require translation and implementation in the specific context. Precise questions tend to arise in the context of a specific research project, which are resource intensive to answer. The ratio of answering an ELSI question is typically 1:3. 1 hour to answer the question, 3 hours to find out what exactly the question is. Activities and tools cannot be maintained by core funding alone and require models of cost-recovery, project involvements and in-kind contributions.

Helpdesks Exchange Platform

In April 2019, a workshop of ELSI Helpdesk and Support Service experts concluded with a shared vision for a federated ELSI Helpdesk, along with collaboration with ELSI services provided by other research infrastructures such as ECRIN and EATRIS:

- mapping of national ELSI service providers within the BBMRI and BMS RI network;
- developing a common framework;
- harmonising procedures and standards of ELSI support services;
- identifying questions that can be addressed on a national level and on a European level;
- undertaking a branding exercise of 'ELSI' in order to develop a common identity and values;
- what it promises and concretizing what it promises and thereby ascertaining of the scope of services provided. This would also assist in ascertaining the scope
- of services provided;
- and sharing of incoming questions and responses.

Running Costs

It is imperative that any tool and expertise proposed and established as a joint service needs to be accurate and sustainable. It responds to the principle that tools developed in the context of research projects need to be maintainable by the core activities of the service and should not duplicate already existing services such as those provided by other RIs or organisations. In conclusion, we commit to implement the collaboration with existing services (such as the BBMRI-ERIC's) and tools (such as ECRIN's Campus tool), either by cross-referencing or integration. Details need to be specified in collaboration agreements, including not only tasks and responsibilities but also upfront clarification of any potential liabilities, competencies, governance and organisation.

ELSI Services & Research: Knowledge Base and Helpdesk

All the activities described above subsequently led to the establishment of the ELSI Knowledge Base and ELSI Helpdesk platform, integrated in the BBMRI ELSI Services & Research unit (Figure 1).

Today, the ELSI Services & Research unit is coordinated by the Headquarters (HQ) of BBMRI-ERIC, and relies on a broad network of ethical, legal and societal experts from both national nodes, national services beyond the biobanking community and in liaison with organisational helpdesk such as the UK's Medical Research Council (MRC) s and other BMS RIs. Predominantly, it chooses its activities based on a consensus among the experts and the National Nodes and whether a service or training courses can be developed out of the (research) activities. Additionally, it provides a platform of knowledge exchange for national, RI ELSI helpdesks to find solutions for challenging requests. Ultimately, it identifies where guidance or training needs to be provided on the ERIC level anew or where signposting to existing solutions is the best option. Activities are taken up only if long-term sustainability of services can be guaranteed.

Figure 1: ELSI Services & Research Unit

The [ELSI Knowledge Base](#) is the open-access resource platform containing information on ELSI related matters relevant in biobanking or clinical trials. The platform is committed to prepare information where needed (e.g. HOW TO GUIDE on governance) or to signpost to already existing resources (e.g., EPDP, GDPR Guidelines) to make it a practical guidance tool and one-stop-shop for researchers.

The [ELSI Helpdesk Network](#) comprises a number of support services and experts across the BBMRI and RI network that assist researchers and research infrastructures with ethical, legal and societal questions. Through the Network, assistance is offered on ELSI topics that are crucial in biobanking and biomedical research, such as informed consent and data protection, amongst others. By sharing

expertise, initial orientation is provided so that the user can navigate through the ethical and legal landscape on both a national and European level (e.g. regular ELSI Helpdesk meetings & exchanges).

How does the ELSI Helpdesk work? Requester have to email to elsi@helpdesk.bbmri-eric.eu and firstly receive an automatic confirmation of receipt. Their enquiry will then be assessed and reviewed by the ELSI Services Officer. Given the customised nature of the ELSI Helpdesk, it may be needed to contact the requester in order to obtain further information. The enquiry is tracked from beginning to end. Given that different countries have different regulatory frameworks, the ELSI Helpdesk network draws from local expert knowledge in order to effectively address your enquiry. It may be possible that the ELSI Helpdesk may also connect the requester to a locally based organisation with the relevant expertise. If the requester has chosen to contact a listed contact point within the ELSI Helpdesk Network, the enquiry will be processed in accordance with their respective operating procedures.

Who is it for? The service is available to researchers and biobanks located in Member and Observer Countries of BBMRI-ERIC¹, as well as any research infrastructures working in the field of life sciences².

What happens after the responds? Much of the information generated from the ELSI Helpdesk will also be beneficial to the wider biobanking community. As a publicly funded research infrastructure, it is important that any knowledge generated is shared. Therefore, responses issued through the ELSI Helpdesk may be used to feed into the ELSI Knowledge Base³, the open access resource platform. Any personal and confidential details will of course be removed.

What is it not? Any information provided by the ELSI Helpdesk is not legal advice. As a research infrastructure, BBMRI-ERIC provides a public service by providing expertise and sharing knowledge regarding ELSI issues for the use and benefit of the biobanking community. Information offered by the ELSI Helpdesk represents one view on the particular ELSI issue raised. It is not intended and should not be taken as the only view on the respective matter. Professional legal advice should always be obtained before taking or refraining from any action as a result of information provided by the ELSI Helpdesk.

Next steps

The proposal has already been largely implemented and is operational. The website of the ELSI Services has been improved to guarantee user-friendliness. It acknowledges CORBEL funding. Dissemination activities have been adapted to improve awareness of the services. Core functionalities (technical and content-wise) will be ensured beyond the CORBEL lifespan by BBMRI-ERIC. Collaboration agreements on shared services are discussed on a bilateral as well as cross-RI level (e.g. AMRI). Partnerships on new content are entered only if the knowledge can be translated in the Knowledge Base for public use (e.g., EUCAN-Connect, CINECA, EOSC-Life). Webinars promote the services such as latest content and knowledge. Dissemination activities will be improved.

¹ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/national-nodes/>

² <http://lifescience-ri.eu/>

³ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/elsi-library>

Publications

- Michaela Th. Mayrhofer and Irene Schlünder. *Biopreservation and Biobanking*. Dec 2018.458-462. <http://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2018.0018>
- ELSI Services Webinar (April 2020) <https://youtu.be/Oc8vHbkdv1k>

References

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- Sariyar M, Schluender I, Smee C, Suhr S. Sharing and Reuse of Sensitive Data and Samples: Supporting Researchers in Identifying Ethical and Legal Requirements. *Biopreserv Biobank*. 2015;13(4):263-270. doi:10.1089/bio.2015.0014

Abbreviations

AMRI	Alliance of Medical Research Infrastructures
BMS	Biological and Medical Sciences
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, Societal Issues
LS	Life Sciences
MRC	Medical Research Council
RI	Research Infrastructure

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed:

No

Adjustments made

None

Appendices

Appendix 1: Development of BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Services

	Common Service ELSI	ELSI Services and Research Unit
Objective	The Common Service ELSI aims to facilitate and support cross-border exchanges of human biological resources and data attached for research uses, collaborations and sharing of knowledge, experiences and best practices. Predominantly, it will provide an ethics check and help-desk.	BBMRI-ERIC is active in the field of ELSI. We support the Biological and Medical Sciences Research Infrastructures, BMS RI community by conducting research, providing services and tools, and offering training with the overall objective of facilitating regulatory compliance and best practice, as well as by influencing European policy.
How it works	Common Services shall be hosted in countries that are BBMRI-ERIC Members. The selection procedure for hosting Common Services shall follow the principles set out in Annex IV.	Operating the basis of the BBMRI-ERIC federated model, we work in partnership with a network of ethical and legal institutions and experts from academia and practice across Europe in Member States.
Selection	Open call for a Common Service	Internal Review and Approval by AoM
Oriented towards	Perform research services for public and private institutions within BBMRI-ERIC member states	Perform research and training services for BMS RIs, incl. public and private institutions
Frequently asked	Basic information National Contact points Concrete question within a research project context	Basic information National Contact points Concrete question within a research project context Training
Management	Federated system with de-centralised coordination Board of Directors, Executive Board, National Experts (linked to National Nodes)	Federated system with centralized coordination Head of Unit, Network of Experts (linked to National Nodes as well as academia and practice)